

The Psalm Project

Discovering the Spiritual World through the Psalms

Psalm 37

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The Goal of this project:

This research project will examine the 150 psalms for the spiritual awareness each Psalm offers. Each Psalm will be examined by its language and the commentary of the Sages. The spiritual awareness analysis will be done in alignment with Ari's definition of the Tree of life, the Book of Creation, and the Zohar. Each verse of the Psalm will be rewritten using the intent of the language and spiritual commentary to convey its spiritual lesson.

The Main Resources:

The Zohar

The Book of Creation

Ari's writing on the Tree of Life and the Ten Sefirot

The Theological Wordbook of the Old Testament

Samson Hirsch's commentary on the Psalms

Tehillim – Psalms – A new translation with a commentary anthologized from the Talmudic and rabbinic sources

Accordance Bible Software

Psalm

New American Standard 1995	Hebrew
<p>Psa. 37:0 <i>A Psalm</i> of David.</p>	<p>Psa. 37:1 לְדָוִד אֶל־תִּתְחַר</p>
<p>Psa. 37:1 "Do not fret because of evildoers,</p>	<p>בְּמִרְעִים אֶל־תִּקְנֵא בְּעֹשֵׂי</p>
<p>Be not ^benvious toward wrongdoers.</p>	<p>עוֹלָה : ² כִּי כִתְצִיר מִהֶרָה</p>
<p>² For they will "wither quickly like the grass</p>	<p>יִמָּלוּ וּכְיִרְק יִשָּׂא יְבוֹלֶזֶן : ³</p>
<p>And ^bfade like the green herb.</p>	<p>בְּטַח בְּיְהוָה וַעֲשֵׂה־טוֹב</p>
<p>³ "Trust in the LORD and do good; ^bDwell in the land and ¹cultivate faithfulness.</p>	<p>שָׁכֵן־אֶרֶץ וּרְעֵה אֲמוֹנָה : ⁴</p>
<p>⁴ "Delight yourself in the LORD; And He will ^bgive you the desires of your heart.</p>	<p>וְהִתְעַנֵּג עַל־יְהוָה וַיִּתֵּן־לְךָ מִשְׁאֵלֹת לִבְּךָ : ⁵ גּוֹל עַל־</p>
<p>⁵ "Commit your way to the LORD, Trust also in Him, and He will do it.</p>	<p>יְהוָה דְּרַכְּךָ וּבְטַח עָלָיו</p>
<p>⁶ He will bring forth "your righteousness as the light</p>	<p>וְהוּא יַעֲשֵׂה : ⁶ וְהוֹצִיא</p>
<p>And your judgment ^bas the noonday.</p>	<p>כְּאוֹר צְדָקָה וּמִשְׁפָּטֶיךָ</p>
<p>Psa. 37:7 ¹Rest in the LORD and "wait ²patiently for Him;</p>	<p>כְּצַהָרִים : ⁷ דָּוָם וְלִיְהוָה</p>
<p>^bDo not fret because of him who "prosperes in his way,</p>	<p>וְהִתְחַוֵּל לּוֹ אֶל־תִּתְחַר</p>
<p>Because of the man who carries out wicked schemes.</p>	<p>בְּמִצְלִיחַ דְּרָכּוֹ בְּאִישׁ עֹשֶׂה</p>
<p>⁸ Cease from anger and "forsake wrath;</p>	<p>מִזְמֹת : ⁸ הִרְרָה מֵאֵף וְעֵזֹב</p>
<p>Do not fret; <i>it leads</i> only to evildoing.</p>	<p>חַמָּה אֶל־תִּתְחַר אֶף־</p>
<p>⁹ For "evildoers will be cut off,</p>	<p>לְהָרַע : ⁹ כִּי־מִרְעִים יִכָּרְתוּן</p>
<p>But those who wait for the LORD, they will ^binherit the land.</p>	<p>וּקְנֵי יְהוָה יִרְשׁוּ־</p>
	<p>אֶרֶץ : ¹⁰ וְעוֹד מֵעַט וְאֵין</p>
	<p>רָשָׁע וְהִתְבוֹנְנֵת עַל־מְקוֹמוֹ</p>

¹⁰ Yet ^aa little while and the wicked man will be no more;

And you will look carefully for ^bhis place and he will not be *there*.

¹¹ But ^athe humble will inherit the land

And will delight themselves in ^babundant prosperity.

Psa. 37:12 The wicked ^aplots against the righteous

And ^bgnashes at him with his teeth.

¹³ The Lord ^alaughs at him, For He sees ^bhis day is coming.

¹⁴ The wicked have drawn the sword and ^abent their bow

To cast down the ^bafflicted and the needy,

To ^cslay those who are upright in conduct.

¹⁵ Their sword will enter their own heart,

And their ^abows will be broken.

Psa. 37:16 ^aBetter is the little of the righteous

Than the abundance of many wicked.

¹⁷ For the ^aarms of the wicked will be broken,

But the LORD ^bsustains the righteous.

¹⁸ The LORD ^aknows the days of the ¹blameless,

And their ^binheritance will be forever.

¹⁹ They will not be ashamed in the time of evil,

And ^ain the days of famine they will have abundance.

וְאֵינְנִי : ¹¹ וְעַנְנִים יִירָשׁוּ-

אֶרֶץ וְהִתְעַנְּגוּ עַל-רֹב

שָׁלוֹם : ¹² זִמָּם רָשָׁע לַצַּדִּיק

וְחָרַק עָלָיו שִׁנָּיו : ¹³ אֲדַנִּי

יִשְׁחַק-לוֹ כִּי-רָאָה כִּי-יָבֵא

יֹמָו : ¹⁴ תָּרַב אִפְתָּחוּ

רָשָׁעִים וְדָרְכוּ קִשְׁתָּם

לְהַפִּיל עָנִי וְאֶבְיוֹן לְטְבוֹת

יִשְׂרָיִל-דָּרְךָ : ¹⁵ תָּרַבְם תָּבוֹא

בְּלִבְכֶם וְקִשְׁתֹּתֶם תִּשְׁבְּרֶנָּה :

¹⁶ טוֹב-מֵעַט לַצַּדִּיק מִתְּמוֹן

רָשָׁעִים רַבִּים : ¹⁷ כִּי זְרוּעוֹת

רָשָׁעִים תִּשְׁבְּרֶנָּה וְסוּמְךָ

צַדִּיקִים יִתְּוָה : ¹⁸ יוֹדֵעַ יְהוָה

יְמֵי תְּמִימָם וְנִחַלְתֶּם לְעוֹלָם

תִּהְיֶה : ¹⁹ לֹא-יִבְשׁוּ בְּעֵת

רָעָה וּבִיְמֵי רַעְבוֹן יִשְׂבְּעוּ :

²⁰ כִּי רָשָׁעִים אֵי אֲבָדוּ וְאֵיבֵי

יְהוָה כִּי-קָר פָּרִים כָּלֹו בְּעַשָׂן

כָּלֹו : ²¹ לַיְּזֵה רָשָׁע וְלֹא

יִשְׁלֹם וְצַדִּיק תּוֹנֵן וְנוֹתֵן : ²²

²⁰ But the ^awicked will perish;
And the enemies of the LORD
will be like the ¹glory of the pastures,
They vanish — ^blike smoke they
vanish away.

²¹ The wicked borrows and does not
pay back,

But the righteous ^ais gracious and
gives.

²² For ^athose blessed by Him will
^binherit the land,

But those ^c cursed by Him will be
cut off.

Psa. 37:23 ^aThe steps of a man
are established by the LORD,

And He ^bdelights in his way.

²⁴ When ^ahe falls, he will not be
hurled headlong,

Because ^bthe LORD is the One
¹who holds his hand.

²⁵ I have been young and now I am
old,

Yet ^aI have not seen the righteous
forsaken

Or ^bhis ¹descendants begging
bread.

²⁶ All day long ^ahe is gracious and
lends,

And ^bhis ¹descendants are a
blessing.

Psa. 37:27 ^aDepart from evil
and do good,

¹So you will abide ^bforever.

²⁸ For the LORD ^aloves ¹justice

And ^bdoes not forsake His godly
ones;

They are ^cpreserved forever,

But the ^{2d}descendants of the
wicked will be cut off.

כִּי מִבְּרָכָיו יִירָשׁוּ אֲרָץ

וּמִקְלָלָיו יִכָּרְתוּ: ²³ מִיְהוָה

מִצְעָדֵי-גֹבֶר כּוֹנְנֵוּ וְדַרְכּוֹ

יִחַפֵּץ: ²⁴ כִּי-יִפֹּל לֹא-יִוָּטֵל

כִּי-יִהְיֶה סוֹמֵךְ יָדוֹ: ²⁵ גַּעַר

הַיְדֵי גַם-זָקְנָתִי וְלֹא-

רָאִיתִי צָדִיק נִעְזֵב וְזָרְעוֹ

מִבְּקֶשׁ-לֶחֶם: ²⁶ כָּל-הַיּוֹם

חֹנֵן וּמְלוֹה וְזָרְעוֹ לְבִרְכָה:

²⁷ סוֹר מֵרַע וַעֲשֵׂה-טוֹב

וְשָׁכֵן לְעוֹלָם: ²⁸ כִּי יִהְיֶה אֶת-

חֲסִידָיו לְעוֹלָם נִשְׁמְרוּ וְזָרַע

רְשָׁעִים נִכְרָת: ²⁹ צָדִיקִים

יִירָשׁוּ-אֲרָץ וְיִשְׁכְּנוּ לְעַד

עָלֶיהָ: ³⁰ כִּי-צָדִיק יִהְיֶה

חֲכָמָה וְלִשׁוֹנוֹ תִדְבֵּר

מִשְׁפָּט: ³¹ תּוֹרַת אֱלֹהֵיו

בְּלִבּוֹ לֹא תִמְעַד אֲשֶׁרֵיו: ³²

צוּפֵה רָשָׁע לְצָדִיק וּמִבְּקֶשׁ

לְהַמִּיתוֹ: ³³ יִהְיֶה לֹא-

29 The righteous will ^ainherit the land
 And ^b dwell in it forever.
 30 The mouth of the righteous
^autters wisdom,
 And his tongue ^bspeaks justice.
 31 The ^alaw of his God is in his heart;
 His ^bsteps do not slip.
 32 The ^awicked spies upon the righteous
 And ^bseeks to kill him.
 33 The LORD will ^anot leave him in his hand
 Or ^blet him be condemned when he is judged.
 34 ^aWait for the LORD and keep His way,
 And He will exalt you to inherit the land;
 When the ^bwicked are cut off, you will see it.

Psa. 37:35 I have ^aseen a wicked, violent man
 Spreading himself like a ^lluxuriant tree in its native soil.

36 Then ¹he passed away, and lo, he ^awas no more;
 I sought for him, but he could not be found.

37 Mark the ^{1a}blameless man, and behold the ^bupright;
 For the man of peace will have a ^{2c}posterity.

38 But transgressors will be altogether ^adestroyed;
 The ¹posterity of the wicked will be ^bcut off.

39 But the ^asalvation of the righteous is from the LORD;

יַעֲזֹבֵנוּ בִּירוֹ וְלֹא יִרְשִׁיעֵנוּ
 בְּהַשְׁפֵּטוֹ : 34 קִנְיָה אֶל־יְהוָה
 וּנְשָׁמַר דְּרָכּוֹ וַיִּרְוּמָמְדָּ
 לְרֵשֶׁת אֲרֶץ בְּהַפְרֹת רְשָׁעִים
 תִּרְאֶה : 35 רָאִיתִי רָשָׁע
 עָרִיץ וּמִתְעַרֵּה כְּאִזְרַח
 רַעֲוֹן : 36 וַיַּעֲבֹר וַהֲנִיחַ אֵינֵנוּ
 וְאֶבְקֵשׁהוּ וְלֹא נִמְצָא : 37
 שָׁמַר־תָּם וִירְאֶה יִשְׂרָאֵל־כִּי־
 אֶחָרִית לְאִישׁ שָׁלוֹם : 38
 וּפְשָׁעִים נִשְׁמְרוּ יַחְדָּו
 אֶחָרִית רְשָׁעִים נִכְרְתָה : 39
 וּתְשׁוּעַת צַדִּיקִים מִיְהוָה
 מִעוֹזָם בְּעֵת צָרָה : 40
 וַיַּעֲזֹרֵם יְהוָה וַיִּפְלְטֵם
 יִפְלְטֵם מִרְשָׁעִים וַיּוֹשִׁיעֵם
 כִּי־תָסוּ בּוֹ :

<p>He is their strength ^bin time of trouble.</p> <p>⁴⁰ ^aThe LORD helps them and delivers them;</p> <p>He ^bdelivers them from the wicked and saves them,</p> <p>Because they ^ctake refuge in Him.</p>	
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References

<p>Psalm 37:1 ^aProv 23:17; 24:19 ^bPs 73:3; Prov 3:31</p> <p>Psalm 37:2 ^aJob 14:2; Ps 90:6; 92:7; James 1:11 ^bPs 129:6</p> <p>Psalm 37:3 ¹Or <i>feed securely or feed on His faithfulness</i> ^aPs 62:8 ^bDeut 30:20 ^cIs 40:11; Ezek 34:13, 14</p> <p>Psalm 37:4 ^aJob 22:26; Ps 94:19; Is 58:14 ^bPs 21:2; 145:19; Matt 7:7, 8</p> <p>Psalm 37:5 ^aPs 55:22; Prov 16:3; 1 Pet 5:7</p> <p>Psalm 37:6 ^aPs 97:11; Is 58:8, 10; Mic 7:9 ^bJob 11:17</p> <p>Psalm 37:7 ¹Or <i>Be still</i> ²Or <i>longingly</i> ^aPs 40:1; 62:5; Lam 3:26 ^bPs 37:1, 8 ^cJer 12:1</p> <p>Psalm 37:8 ^aEph 4:31; Col 3:8</p>	<p>Psalm 37:9 ^aPs 37:2, 22 ^bPs 25:13; Prov 2:21; Is 57:13; 60:21; Matt 5:5</p> <p>Psalm 37:10 ^aJob 24:24 ^bJob 7:10; Ps 37:35, 36</p> <p>Psalm 37:11 ^aMatt 5:5 ^bPs 72:7</p> <p>Psalm 37:12 ^aPs 31:13, 20 ^bPs 35:16</p> <p>Psalm 37:13 ^aPs 2:4 ^b1 Sam 26:10; Job 18:20</p> <p>Psalm 37:14 ^aPs 11:2; Lam 2:4 ^bPs 35:10; 86:1 ^cPs 11:2</p> <p>Psalm 37:15 ^a1 Sam 2:4; Ps 46:9</p> <p>Psalm 37:16 ^aProv 15:16; 16:8</p> <p>Psalm 37:17 ^aJob 38:15; Ps 10:15; Ezek 30:21 ^bPs 71:6; 145:14</p>
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Psalm 37:18

¹Lit *complete; or perfect*

^aPs 1:6; 31:7

^bPs 37:27, 29

Psalm 37:19

^aJob 5:20; Ps 33:19

Psalm 37:20

¹i.e. flowers

^aPs 73:27

^bPs 68:2; 102:3

Psalm 37:21

^aPs 112:5, 9

Psalm 37:22

^aProv 3:33

^bPs 37:9

^cJob 5:3

Psalm 37:23

^a1 Sam 2:9; Ps 40:2; 66:9; 119:5

^bPs 147:11

Psalm 37:24

¹Or *who sustains him with His hand*

^aPs 145:14; Prov 24:16; Mic 7:8

^bPs 147:6

Psalm 37:25

¹Lit *seed*

^aPs 37:28; Is 41:17; Heb 13:5

^bPs 109:10

Psalm 37:26

¹Lit *seed*

^aDeut 15:8; Ps 37:21

^bPs 147:13

Psalm 37:27

¹Or *And dwell forever*

^aPs 34:14

^bPs 37:18; 102:28

Psalm 37:28

¹Lit *judgment*

²Lit *seed*

^aPs 11:7; 33:5

^bPs 37:25

^cPs 31:23

^dPs 21:10; 37:9; Prov 2:22; Is 14:20

Psalm 37:29

^aPs 37:9; Prov 2:21

^bPs 37:18

Psalm 37:30

^aPs 49:3; Prov 10:13

^bPs 101:1; 119:13

Psalm 37:31

^aDeut 6:6; Ps 40:8; 119:11; Is 51:7; Jer 31:33

^bPs 26:1; 37:23

Psalm 37:32

^aPs 10:8; 17:11

^bPs 37:14

Psalm 37:33

^aPs 31:8; 2 Pet 2:9

^bPs 34:22; 109:31

Psalm 37:34

^aPs 27:14; 37:9

^bPs 52:5, 6; 91:8

Psalm 37:35

¹Lit *native*; Heb obscure

^aJob 5:3; Jer 12:2

^bJob 8:16

Psalm 37:36

¹Ancient versions read *I passed by*

^aJob 20:5; Ps 37:10

Psalm 37:37

¹Lit *complete*; or *perfect*

²Lit *an end*

^aPs 37:18

^bPs 7:10

^cIs 57:1, 2

Psalm 37:38

¹Lit *end*

^aPs 1:4-6; 37:20, 28

^bPs 37:9; 73:17

Psalm 37:39

^aPs 3:8; 62:1

^bPs 9:9; 37:19

Psalm 37:40

^aPs 54:4

^bPs 22:4; Is 31:5; Dan 3:17; 6:23

^c1 Chr 5:20; Ps 34:22

Targum

Psa. 37:1 Of David. Have no desire for malefactors, to be like them; and do not be jealous of those who commit oppression, to join with them. ² Because their end will be like plants, quickly will they wither; and like the green grass they will fall away. ³ Trust in the word of the LORD and do good; dwell in the land and be strong in faith. ⁴ And you will delight in the LORD, and he will give you the requests of your heart. ⁵ Reveal to the LORD your ways, and trust in his word, and he will act. ⁶ And your righteousness will come out like light, and your judgment like noonday. ⁷ Be quiet in the presence of the LORD and wait for him; do not desire the wicked man who prospers his way, the man who follows the counsel of sinners. ⁸ Wait without anger and forsake wrath; do not long indeed to do evil. ⁹ For those who do evil will be destroyed; but those who hope in the word of the LORD – they will inherit the land. ¹⁰ And yet a little while, and there is no wicked man; you will look carefully at his place, and he is not. ¹¹ But the humble will inherit the land; and they will delight in the plenitude of peace. ¹² The wicked man plots harm against the righteous man, and grinds his teeth against him. ¹³ The LORD will laugh at him, for he has seen, for the day of his ruin has come. ¹⁴ The wicked have drawn the sword and bent their bows to kill the humble and lowly, to slaughter the upright of way. ¹⁵ Their blade will enter their [own] heart, and their bows will break. ¹⁶ Better in the presence of the LORD is the smallness of the righteous man than the multitude of many wicked men. ¹⁷ For the arms of the wicked will be broken, but the word of the LORD supports the righteous. ¹⁸ The days of the blameless are known in the LORD's presence, and their inheritance will last forever. ¹⁹ They will not be ashamed in the time of evil, and in the days of famine they are satisfied. ²⁰ For the wicked will perish, and the enemies of the LORD are like the glory of young sheep that at first are fattened but finally slaughtered – likewise the wicked will perish and be destroyed in the smoke of Gehenna. ²¹ The wicked borrows and does not repay; but the

righteous is compassionate, and gives. ²² For those who are blessed by his word will inherit the land; but those who are cursed by death will be destroyed. ²³ In the presence of the LORD the steps of a man are made firm, and he will favor his ways. ²⁴ For when he falls into sickness, he will not die, because the LORD is the helper at his hand. ²⁵ I was a boy, but have grown old; and I have not seen the righteous man abandoned or his sons seeking bread because of want. ²⁶ For all the day he is compassionate and lends; and his seed is for a blessing. ²⁷ Turn from evil, and practice kindness, and abide for eternal life. [ANOTHER TARGUM: Turn from doing evil, O righteous man, and do good; because of this you will abide forever.] ²⁸ For the LORD loves justice and will not abandon his pious ones; they are protected forever; but the sons of the wicked will be destroyed. ²⁹ The righteous will inherit the land, and will dwell on it forever. ³⁰ The mouth of the righteous murmurs wisdom, and his tongue speaks justice. ³¹ The law (nimus) of his God is in his heart; his feet do not stumble. ³² The wicked man observes the righteous man and seeks to kill him. ³³ The LORD will not abandon him into his hand, and will not find him guilty when he is judged. [ANOTHER TARGUM: When he stands in judgment.] ³⁴ Hope in the word of the LORD, and keep his way, and he will raise you up to inherit the land; you will see the destruction of the wicked. ³⁵ I have seen the wicked man, strong and mighty, like a native and leafy tree. ³⁶ And he ceased from the world, and, behold, he is no more; and I sought him but he was not found. ³⁷ Preserve blamelessness, and behold, honesty; for the end of [such] a son of man is peace. ³⁸ But rebels will be destroyed together; the end of the wicked is destruction. ³⁹ But the redemption of the righteous is from the presence of the LORD, their strength in the time of trouble. ⁴⁰ And the LORD helped them and saved them, he saved them from sinners; and he will redeem them, for they trusted in his word.

Spiritual Awareness

Introduction

In this Psalm, David described the forces of evil which strive to convince humans that there is no God. Evil people point to their success as evidence that no Supreme Being is watching what they are doing.

Verse one

Do not become perturbed because wicked people seem to have good fortune. Gevurah will issue punishment on the wicked in time. It is challenging to watch evil people break the laws of the LORD and the government, and they get away with it. Where is divine intervention? The Zohar says that the LORD gives evil people time to correct their evil ways and ask for repentance. Unfortunately, there are plenty of people who never change their ways. Guvurah may not affect them in their lifetime, but the LORD tells us that Guvurah will get involved on judgment day. Sins that are not unrepented will appear on the list that the LORD will use on judgment day. The righteous will have an empty list. The wicked will have a long list. Keep faith in the LORD that justice will happen.

Verse two

Green herbs ripen shortly after they are planted. This plant does not grow deep, sturdy roots in the soil. They ripen and die quickly.

Verse three

Have faith in the LORD because you will feel secure and aware of His presence. The LORD loves the people who want to belong to Him and follow His Torah.

Verse four

Seek and find your greatest joy in the presence of the LORD. The heart's desire is the need to feel that the LORD is surrounding righteous people.

Verse five

This verse is a parallel verse to verse four. Parallel verses are repeated verses for emphasis. Why would you place yourself on any path that the LORD has not laid out for you?

Verse six

This verse reminds us that one must commit their life to the LORD. Trust in the LORD that He is watching out for you.

Verse seven

One should refrain from all speech, complaints, and protests about wicked people. The fate of the righteous will at times seem incomprehensible. One must accept that wicked people will get away with their evil, and the righteous cannot do anything to stop it.

Verse eight

This is a parallel verse to verse seven.

Verse nine

Evildoers' apparent success with help brings about their eventual downfall. Wait for the LORD to send Gevurah upon the evildoers. The new Heaven and earth will be for the righteous. The wicked will be cased out to Sheol.

Verse ten

The life of the wicked is usually short. If their evil comes to light within the confines of the government's law, then they will be punished by their peers. It is true that there were and are wicked people who live long lives and stay out of the bounds of the government's laws. Gevurah will eventually punish these people.

Verse eleven

In time the righteous and wicked will be separated, and the wicked will be cast into Sheol.

Verse twelve to fifteen

The ways of the righteous people infuriate wicked people—the wicked stand in opposition to the righteous. Eventually, Gevurah will step in and assist the wicked to destroy themselves.

Verse sixteen

מְהָמוֹן (mehamon) – means “abundance” or “sound.” David could have referred to the abundance of property the wicked accumulate or the noise that they make. Wicked people tend to complain about everything that does not entirely fit into their expectations. The LORD likes the sound of the righteous person’s voice and dislikes the noise of the wicked.

Verse seventeen

This verse repeats earlier verses. Gevurah will break the arms of the wicked as they are judged and sent to Sheol.

Verse eighteen

The LORD is aware of the wicked and will give them their inheritance. That inheritance is an eternity in the depths of Sheol.

Verse nineteen

Wicked people do not feel ashamed for their evil during their lives. Usually, wicked people justify their actions as righteous. They will never accept that their ways were evil. Thus, they never repent, for they are not ashamed. Unfortunately, during famine days, they will not go hungry because they have accumulated what they need to survive. That is fine for that time. The righteous know that wicked peoples’ final journey is to Sheol, and they will be cut off from the LORD’s love and grace forever.

Verse twenty

This verse describes the penalty for the wicked as described in verse nineteen.

Verse twenty-one

Everything a person owns is a gift from the LORD. Eventually, life ends, and the properties and monies one accumulates over a lifetime will go to someone else. Righteous people understand this. They also understand that blessings that shower down from Heaven are meant to be shared with other people.

Verse twenty-two

The divine blessing of eternal life with the LORD in Heaven will be won through a life of following the ways of the Torah.

Verse twenty-three & twenty-four

The righteous person walks in the steps that the LORD has laid out. The wicked person walks in the steps that he/she decides to follow.

Verse twenty-five

In the years of David's life from birth to when he wrote this Psalm, he never witnessed a righteous person forsaken by the LORD.

Verse twenty-six

When the LORD sends blessings from Heaven, the righteous person will share those blessings with his/her fellow human.

Verse twenty-seven through twenty-nine

Always do good and avoid evil. By doing so, the righteous will dwell with the LORD forever.

Verse thirty

Wisdom comes to the righteous.

Verse thirty-one

The righteous person is wise being full of wisdom because the Torah is in his/her heart.

Verse thirty-two

Evil people are the implacable foe of the righteous because of the difference in their philosophies of life and their attitudes toward their neighbors. Loving one's neighbor means that one never cheats or steals from their neighbor. The wicked see no problem stealing and cheating from their neighbor.

Verse thirty-three

If a wicked person captures a righteous person, the LORD will not leave the righteous person in the hands of the adversary. The LORD will not let the righteous be condemned when the world reaches the final judgment from Gevurah.

Verse thirty-four

There will be a day when the wicked are removed from the earth and sent to Sheol. The LORD will give the righteous the new Heaven and new earth when that day comes.

Verse thirty-five

David said that he had witnessed wicked people, yet they seemed to prosper.

Verse thirty-six

When a wicked person dies, that person is disconnected from the LORD because the person is sent to Sheol.

Verse thirty-seven through forty

These verses summarize the Psalm. Wicked people may look prosperous, but there will come a time when Gevurah will judge them and send them to Sheol. In Sheol, they will be disconnected from the LORD for eternity. The righteous may not possess as many material things, but they will be filled with spiritual things. They will eventually live an eternity with the LORD.

Appendix

Mystical Methodology to Prayer

All prayers result in spiritual energy which rises through the conduits that connect Sefirot realms. The "answer" to prayers is the transformation of spiritual energy from its original frequency to an appropriate frequency which will give the necessary results.

MHK V5 1/17/2016

Chambers of Aba and Ima of Briyah

Keter: prayers of thanksgiving come

